

BIMac 2026

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INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE
ON MACROMOLECULES

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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METALOGRAFIU

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TOC analýza | AOX/EOX | TN/TK/TS | CHNSO rezačky XRF
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EDITORIAL

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Bratislava, 2026

On behalf of the organizing committee, it is our great pleasure to welcome you to the XXIV. Bratislava International Conference on Macromolecules – BIMac 2026, organized by the Polymer Institute of the Slovak Academy of Sciences. This long-standing conference series, established in 1968, continues to provide an important international platform for discussing advances in polymer science and related disciplines.

The conference brings together researchers, students, and industry professionals to share their latest scientific results and exchange ideas in key areas of polymer science, including the synthesis and characterization of polymers, composite polymeric materials, polymeric biomaterials, and molecular simulations of polymers. These diverse topics reflect the dynamic, interdisciplinary nature of modern macromolecular research and its growing relevance to both fundamental science and practical applications.

This conference is also dedicated to our former colleague, Dr. Mária Omastová, in recognition of her distinguished career, significant contributions to polymer science, and continuous inspiration and support for colleagues and young scientists.

Beyond the scientific program, we believe that conferences are also about people—about the conversations that continue after presentations, the new collaborations that arise during poster discussions, and the friendships that begin over coffee breaks or social events. We sincerely hope this meeting will create a stimulating environment where new ideas emerge and lasting professional partnerships form.

This year's conference takes place in the beautiful surroundings of the High Tatras, providing a unique opportunity to combine scientific exchange with moments of relaxation and inspiration in nature. Surrounded by mountains and the fresh alpine air, we encourage you not only to actively engage in the scientific sessions but also to enjoy the region's natural beauty, the hospitality and wellness facilities at the conference venue, and the informal social activities prepared for participants.

We hope that BIMac 2026 will be an inspiring and memorable event for all participants—scientifically rewarding, intellectually stimulating, and personally enriching. May this meeting strengthen our scientific community and open the door to new collaborations and friendships.

We wish you a productive conference, stimulating discussions, and an enjoyable stay in the High Tatras.

Dr. Zdenko Špitálsky
Chair of BIMac 2026

FROM NANOMATERIAL TO FUNCTIONAL COATINGS: HYDROPHOBIC CARBON QUANTUM DOTS WITH PHOTODYNAMIC ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY

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Quantum dots are still considered a relatively new class of nanomaterials, although their origins can be traced back to ancient times. They can be classified into several categories depending on the synthesis method, the precursors used, their final structure, and their intended application [1]. In our research, we focus specifically on hydrophobic carbon quantum dots, which have been extensively characterized using a wide range of analytical techniques.

These materials' function based on the principles of photodynamic therapy, utilizing a common low-intensity LED diode as the irradiation source. Upon irradiation, they generate reactive oxygen species (ROS), particularly singlet oxygen. Hydrophobic carbon quantum dots can be incorporated into various polymer matrices, textiles, and coating systems.

Their antimicrobial efficacy has been confirmed by several internationally recognized research groups. At the same time, ecotoxicological studies indicate that these materials do not adversely affect the viability of small organisms in different ecosystems. Current research is therefore increasingly focused on their application in antimicrobial coatings, particularly for frequently contaminated surfaces such as those found in public transport systems, the aviation industry, and other high-contact surfaces [2].

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- [2] Meier P., et al. Ecotoxicol. Environ. Saf. 2025, 300, 118421.

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